
THE USE OF EXPERT TESTIMONY IN CASES OF MENTAL HEALTH AND INSANITY

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ABSTRACT

Evidently, the mental health specialists' testimony in criminal cases relates tremendously to different matters that arise during the interpreter stage. However, it should be pointed out that not all the material produced in an expert's practice may be regarded as highly valid and comprehensible for the case. Depending on the nature and circumstances of the particular case, forensic mental health expertise (FMHE) means that useful information is reported to the decision-makers in the criminal justice system. Its use can be made particularly in following conclusions in criminal trials; is evaluations of criminal responsibility, and decisions on the right retributive action. Despite the increased attention to the study of FMHE, the effect that this expertise has on the outcomes of judicial proceedings is yet unrecognized in terms of how and to what extent.² Experts such as psychologists and psychiatrists are more often being called into the court to offer insight that may help the triers of fact come to a judgment of the accused's legal lunacy during the time of the alleged crime.³ The paper also informs the historical background of expert witnesses, the legal criteria that befits them, and the issues they encounter.

Keywords: criminal law, expert opinion, insanity, medical, legal, psychiatry, Criminal responsibility, Indian Penal Code

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² R.M.S. van Es, M.J.J. Kunst, J.W. de Keijser, *Forensic mental health expert testimony and judicial decision-making: A systematic literature review*, *Aggression and Violent Behavior*, Volume 51, 101387, (2020). ISSN 1359-1789, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2020.101387>.

³ Redding, R. E., Floyd, M. Y., & Hawk, G. L. *What judges and lawyers think about the testimony of mental health experts: a survey of the courts and bar*. *Behavioral sciences & the law*, 19(4), 583–594, (2001). <https://doi.org/10.1002/bsl.455>

I. INTRODUCTION

The interrelatedness of mental health issues and criminal justice has remained one of the most burning issues in society as well as in law. The motivation to comprehend the legal processes that happen at the crossroads between psychiatry and law is relatively low; however, they appear more often in the area of justice than in other branches of medicine. The lawyers determine that psychiatrists should be taken to court for failing to honour contracts, performing negligent acts, either medical or criminal, and for infringement of patients' rights. Forensic psychiatry refers to a subspecialty of psychiatry that endeavours to regulate the interface between law and mental health emphasizing issues to do with the mental state of offenders. Court work is a relatively common field of work for psychiatrists as many of them are expert witnesses. The increasing engagement of present-day mental health professionals within the legal domain implies increased responsibility and the capacity for harm. Expert cognition is the knowledge that has been given to support the authority of an expert's opinion. Even though it is not directly related to the circumstances of the case the qualification does permit the expert's opinion to be used as evidence. When people state that they committed certain acts due to a mental disorder or that they lacked the capacity of a rational mind before the commission of the alleged offence, it sets a complex legal process that often entails the assistance of psychiatrists or other experts in that field. Expert witness and related issues in the legal systems important specifically to issues of mental health and insanity is still a vibrant and basic aspect of civil and criminal justice systems today in an effort to balance the equally essential quest for equity with the provision of justice's recognition of any given party's vulnerability to mental health challenges.

- *How have legal standards for insanity defences evolved over time, and how do they shape the use of expert testimony in furtherance of some recent legal reforms or landmark cases that have impacted the practice of using expert testimony in cases of mental health and insanity?*

II. RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

In order to address the research objective, I went through articles, blogs, etc on the insanity defence, Mc Naughten rule, and criminal insanity. In order to enhance inclusivity, additional terminology The cross-references of significant publications and reviews were thoroughly examined, whenever applicable. To conduct searches pertaining to legal matters, mostly

secondary data sources were used. The utilisation of many databases, including, Ebsco Host, Manupatra, Hein Online, Lexis Nexis, Jstor, Springer Link, and SCC online, proved to be beneficial for doing online searches. I discovered a significant dispersion of published articles and case laws. In order to facilitate a meaningful conversation, and only pertinent articles were chosen for the evaluation.

III. LITERATURE REVIEW

1. To what extent should expert psychiatric witnesses comment on criminal culpability? ⁴

During trials, an important role is given to the evaluation of the mental state of a defendant with the purpose accomplished by expert psychiatric testimony. Nevertheless, in order for such evidence to be deemed as relevant and thereby admitted into trial, it should be beyond the cognitive perceptions of a judge and/or jurors. It is professionals' business to direct important questions and affairs, like a defendant's purpose or guilt, not for the court. This is important in determining the extent of the blame of the accused so that the right approach, and the possibility of a lighter punishment for mental health patients, can be attained. This might worsen if a person has a mental disorder; the punishment will be more severe compared to a person with no illness. In the criminal justice procedure, the assessment of the defendant's level of responsibility remains one of the essential elements although the relationship between a mental condition and responsibility remains rather vague. Although expert opinion is a critical element, there is the possibility of judges requesting psychiatrists to state their opinion about the degree of the patient's culpability. This should be resisted on the same notes of prejudice affecting the conclusion and the court's ruling on the guilt and defect of responsibility.

2. Expert Testimony in insanity cases⁵

Mr. Eric Clark, who was diagnosed of schizophrenia at the age of 17, shot dead Police Officer; Jeffrey Moritz in the year 2000 in Flagstaff, Arizona. The prior ruling of the Arizona Supreme Court, in the decision made in the Furman case, precluded instructions allowing the possibility of damaging the existence of a deliberate intention, therefore limiting Clark's opportunity to present solid proofs of mental illness, which would have proven the absence of criminal intent.

⁴ 1. Hallett N., *To what extent should expert psychiatric witnesses comment on criminal culpability?* *Medicine, Science, and the Law*, 60(1):67-74, (2020). doi:10.1177/0025802419872844

⁵ Cynthia Calkins Mercado, *Expert testimony in insanity cases*, Vol 37, No. 10, APA, pg-59, (2006).
<https://www.apa.org/monitor/nov06/jn>

The APA and the AAPL have filed a brief on behalf of Clark pointing out that the right to due process entails an opportunity to introduce evidence that may negate the mental status part of an offense. The Supreme Court supported Arizona, as the question was regarding the due process, and it was stated that it is up to the individual states on how an insanity threshold is defined and there is no definite requirement on the formulation of an insanity that is to be met to ensure the subject is given due process.

IV. HISTORICAL OVERVIEW

Earlier, Mental health conditions were actually believed to be due to reasons of spiritual presence or lack of it, lack of moral character, or some form of weakness. Earlier, primary legal systems existing in various regions of the world had no proper concept of mental illness, and individuals who were labelled as 'insane' were often exposed to stiff penalties and other torturous measures as the societies involved appeared entirely uncomfortable with addressing mental disease and criminal responsibility as two related but different issues. However, it has been a drastic transformation in including the testimony of mental health doctors as cultures evolved and had a systematic understanding of mental illness, as did legal provisions for assessing it. The historical development of the insanity defense complimented by the Modern incorporation of expert evidence is the improvement of tackling mental health or criminal responsibility in the existing legal systems.

V. PSYCHIATRY VIS-À-VIS CRIMINAL RESPONSIBILITY

It is thus important to discuss the connection between psychiatry and criminal responsibility as psychiatry is a key to assessing the condition of the participant in the delict and determining his/her degree of culpability as provided by criminal law. The law provides much significance to criminal responsibility and often the psychiatric evaluation is carried out to understand the level at how the mental condition of the defendant affects the behaviour, psychiatry exerts a considerable influence on criminal conduct, and on the basis of this law, differentiates one criminal from the other. Criminal responsibility serves as a mechanism for evaluating criminal behaviour and establishing the guilt or innocence of an individual. An intentional act or omission that is undertaken without any defence or justification, in violation of criminal law,

and is punishable as a felony or misdemeanour.⁶ The source is a publication by Paul W. Tappan in the year 1960. The Latin phrase 'Actus non facit reum nisi mens sit rea' represents the fundamental principle of criminal law. It encompasses both the cognitive and physical components of the crime's parts. Mens rea refers to an individual's awareness that their activity is criminal, while actus reus refers to the actual physical act.

The capacity assessment seeks to evaluate a criminal defendant's level of rational understanding in order to determine their ability to effectively communicate with their legal counsel and their accurate and true awareness of the legal processes being brought against them.

VI. ASSESSING THE MENTAL AND LEGAL COMPETENCE OF INDIVIDUALS IN CRIMINAL PROCEEDINGS

Understanding the actions, motives and admissibility of an individual or an organisation and defining their capability of being legally liable or the legal validity of a civil business transaction is a key matter. The sum total of such elements is the Institute of legal ability. As is the case with any distinction, a substantial difference lies between medical capacity and legal capacity. The former is intrinsically bound with the subject's mental capacity, whereas the latter, the legal part, relates to the subject's perception and the intentions, which accompany or precede an action or inaction on their part. Thus, it can be understood that there are cases when the medical and legal conditions do not overlap. Thus, mental health condition does not necessarily imply that the affected will have some signs of the sickness. Nevertheless, in relation to a specific act or dealing, such a person may be considered legally inept or on the other hand, a person who is mentally ill can be regarded as legally savvy.⁷ Under such condition, the fields of medical and legal sciences become one since it is processed under the same procedure. Hence, it is undesirable to justify the verdict of a particular judge when examining the issue of a person's capacity. An impartial individual does not possess any special or medical skills, as discussed before.

⁶ Math, S. B., Kumar, C. N., & Moirangthem, S. *Insanity Defense: Past, Present, and Future*. Indian journal of psychological medicine, 37(4), 381–387, (2015). <https://doi.org/10.4103/0253-7176.168559>

⁷ R J Bonnie; C Slobogin, *Role of mental health professionals in the criminal process-the case for informed speculation*, Volume: 66 Issue: 3, Virginia Law Review, (96) 427-522, (1980).

VII. THE RELEVANCE AND ADMISSIBILITY OF EXPERT OPINION WITH REGARD TO INSANITY AND MENTAL HEALTH IN ACCORDANCE WITH INDIAN LAW

The Indian legal system has procedural guidelines for expert opinions in court, which are elucidated by the Bharatiya Sakshya Adhinyam and the Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita. An expert is a person who knows a lot about a particular subject. Evidence is information or ideas from people that can prove something or disprove it. Expert evidence is the knowledge or opinion of an expert in a special field. It can be relied upon to provide proof on issues that are under investigation whether they are legal or factual.⁸

When dealing with insanity two main questions arise: (a) Was the offender mentally ill at the time he committed the act? And (b) Did his mental condition make it impossible for him to know what he was doing, its nature and consequences?

Section 328 of the Nagarik Suraksha Sanhita lays out the steps to take when handling a person with mental illness. This section states that a Magistrate who thinks someone has mental instability and can't defend themselves must set up an exam. The civil surgeon of the district or another doctor chosen by the Government will carry out this exam.

As per the M'Naghten Rules,⁹ which form the foundation of the Indian Criminal Law regarding insanity under Section 84 of The Indian Penal Code, 1860, a medical witness who has been present in court and heard the evidence may be asked, based on scientific principles, whether the facts presented by the witness, assuming them to be true, indicate a mental state that is unable to differentiate between right and wrong.

An expert with the appropriate academic credentials can offer an opinion on the accused's condition of mind or the findings from the tests carried out whether they observed the accused give the statements or not. In this way, such a witness is capable of stating how, in their opinion, certain factual circumstances might work in a particular case, even if the witness has no personal experience encountering the accused. A psychiatrist who may have examined the defendant with regards to the offence after the act may testify about the state of the defendant at the time he or she gave the evaluation and more so, whether he or she had the condition at

⁸ Van Es, R., Kunst, M., & De Keijser, J. (2020, March 1). *Forensic mental health expert testimony and judicial decision-making: A systematic literature review*. Aggression and Violent Behavior; Elsevier BV.

<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.avb.2020.101387>

⁹ M'Naghten's Case 8 ER 178 Volume 8

the time of the offence.¹⁰ The expert can also come with an opinion and testify whether the accused inmate is not faking or acting merely insane. The question has to be raised, an honest man with no connection to the accused can sit in a trial and only read the trial's transcript, yet, the man has the right to his opinion derived from uncontested and clear evidence. The pertinent sections of the regulations are outlined as follows:

It is formulated as 'Where is x?' Here the word 'is' stands for 'exists' while other words represent locations, objects, or even people that can be positioned and designated by coordinates. 11

1) The principle of individual liberty – this presupposes that every individual has a right to his/her liberty and has a rational soul that must first be proved to be insane. Speaking of the defense used by the accused during a Criminal trial, the defence of insanity can be employed here in a way the accused can prove that at the time of committing a certain act, he/she was suffering from mental illness and as such, (a) did not know that what he/she was doing was either wrong or contrary to the law or (b) despite appreciating that what he/she was doing was wrong, the accused did not know. Therefore, the evidence in chief of a doctor who has only observed the accused during the trial cannot be used as evidence of the contested fact of the accused's state of mind. Though where facts are either undisputed or are issues that do not require the evaluation of the community, the defences may turn to the medical evidence for analysis thereof as opposed to a right.

VIII. JUDICIAL RESPONSE

The expert's view is guided by the essential idea that it is necessary for the expert to have evidence supporting their judgement, and that the result should be measurable. The court should evaluate the expert's opinion in the same manner as any other form of evidence.

The challenge arises when the admission asserts that the defendant is abnormal, and the issue at hand is whether, during the relevant period, they were mentally defective to the extent that they were unable to differentiate between right and wrong. The court requires the assistance of mental experts in order to reach the correct conclusion.

¹⁰ Lassen, G., *The Psychologist as an Expert Witness in Assessing Mental Disease or Defect*, American Bar Association Journal, 50(3), 239–242, (1964). <http://www.jstor.org/stable/25722722>

¹¹ Winfred Overholser, *Psychiatric Expert Testimony in Criminal Cases Since McNaghten--A Review*, 42 J. Crim. L.Criminology & Police Sci. 283 (1951-1952)

The court in the case of *Deo Rao v. Emperor*¹² established that an expert's judgement is pertinent in legal matters concerning scientific matters and mental illnesses. The court upheld Dr. Roy's opinion by stating and concluding that 'We accept the opinion of Dr Roy and other evidence in the case and hold that the accused by reasons of unsoundness of mind did not know the nature of the act or that what he was doing was either wrong or contrary to the law established legal insanity within the meaning of section 84, Indian penal code.'

The court in *Baswant Rao's* case deliberated on the defendant's mental state, namely determining his legal sanity or insanity. Justice Hidayatullah contended that a previous ruling is inconsequential when understanding the testimony of an expert. Nevertheless, a psychiatric evaluation is neither definitive nor necessary for an Indian court to make a determination in a mental health case. The court should thoroughly examine the expert's report and take into account the absence of a psychiatric evaluation of the accused as a crucial factor in acquitting them, if other evidence and circumstances raise a reasonable doubt regarding the accused's mental state.

IX. ANALYSIS

In India, the jury trial system does not exist, hence the Judge is solely accountable for both the ultimate decision and the assessment of the evidence. Nevertheless, the Judge's lack of expertise in mental well-being and related matters does not undermine the significance of the psychiatric expert opinion.

It is reasonable to expect that such evidence should be allowed to be presented in court whenever it is pertinent to the court's ultimate ruling.¹³ In order to modify the accused's criminal liability, it is essential to comprehend and apply the concepts of criminal responsibility. Adhering to the principles of psychiatry that prioritize the assessment of culpability is an essential component in embracing a more interdisciplinary methodology. To

¹² *Emperor vs Deorao Bhivaji*, (1935) 37 BOMLR 191

¹³ Elizabeth Egbert, Brie Pileggi-Valleen, *Expert Testimony on Settled Insanity*, *Journal of the American Academy of Psychiatry and the Law*, 50 (2) 308-310, Online Jun 2022.

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accomplish this, legislators and professionals must establish a connection between the concepts of legal and medical insanity.¹⁴

X. CONCLUSION

Crime is a multifarious idea that cannot be explained simply of psychological explanations. However, the court's approach to accepting psychological medical proof was not consistent; at times such evidence was allowed and sometimes not. Strict attention to the right and wrong element of criminal responsibility has been principally responsible for maintaining an unsubstantial significance of expert opinion on mental health and insanity as evidence.

In order to unite law and psychiatry and to define an interdisciplinary framework, that recognizes free will and moral accountability, a fundamental adjustment has to be undertaken in the legal system. The introduction of forensic psychiatry requires to be undertaken as a collaborative attempt by many agencies and regulatory entities in the Indian criminal justice structure. The inclusion of expert opinion in insanity and mental health cases should be done more widely and properly in a standardised and verified form. The application of research and teaching may be a leap forward in the blending of law and psychiatry, enabling a new beginning in the domain of psychiatry and law.

REFERENCES

- Ratanlal & Dhirajlal, (2019), The Indian Evidence Act, twenty-seventh edition, Lexis Nexis.
- Frank Bates, (1977), "Admissibility: Psychiatric Evidence: Towards a Coherent Policy".
- Alec Samuels (1981), "Psychiatric Evidence", Crim. L.R. 762 at 762-763
- Daniel W. Shuman, (2014), Psychiatric And Psychological Evidence, South Asian Edition, Thomson West.

¹⁴ Overholser, W., *Psychiatric Expert Testimony in Criminal Cases since McNaghten. A Review*, The Journal of Criminal Law, Criminology, and Police Science, 42(3), 283–299, (1951). <https://doi.org/10.2307/1140344>

- Ratanlal & Dhirajlal, (2020) Criminal Procedure Code, twenty-third edition, Lexis Nexis.